

The Intersectionality of Being the “Other”: Doris Lessing's "An Old Woman and Her Cat"

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There's a sense of significance in labels for every group because defining is closely tied to a feeling of belonging and unity. However, these boundaries that societies place usually come from a place of exclusion rather than inclusion - because to understand what you are, you first have to establish what you aren't. This is where theories such as abjection and commodity fetishism come into play, as both of them explore how societies define belonging and identity through a lens of value. In the case of Doris Lessing's "An Old Woman and Her Cat," the readers get a glimpse of not only the external but the inner workings of both. This adorable-titled story about a "weird" Romani woman and her also weird companion brings not only dark social commentary about the state of discrimination based on ethnicity but also financial status and the internal turmoil faced by the "Other."

Abjection and commodity fetishism work well together to explain the marginalization of people in a society. In the case of this story, they combine to throw the main character even deeper into the bottomless pit of alienation. In the essay "Powers of Horror," Julia Kristeva, a famous linguist, philosopher, psychoanalyst, and feminist writer discusses the theory of abjection. "The term means "the state of being cast off," and according to Kristeva, it is a feeling of disgust, filth, and humiliation, things we tend to reject for becoming subjects."(Jönsson, 2023). The next applied framework, commodity fetishism, " is the process by which social relations among people are obscured, and the relationships between commodities take precedence. This phenomenon leads to a distorted perception of the nature of value and the underlying social dynamics within a capitalist society."("Commodity Fetishism," n.d.). Both theories perfectly encapsulate the main character, Hetty's, and her cat's life by proxy. The fascinating aspect of the story is that she is an abject not only because of her ethnicity but also her financial situation and her authentic personality as a whole, as she starts being marginalized

more when she quits her conventional job and starts pursuing her true passions. Her story is also one of deep-rooted, internalized abjection, the manifestation of which is seen even from her own family.

The first and primary concern that her family brings up with Hetty's identity is her heritage. We learn that her mother was a Romani woman who decided to marry outside the culture and "live in an actual house." This introductory sentence already sets up a large part of the story and Hetty's identity, foreshadowing the inevitable issues she'd face as someone who is closely related to a systematically alienated group of people. When we're introduced to her familial background, we quickly learn that she's been shunned by her kids simply because of her Romani heritage and "weirdness," which isn't clearly defined in the story but could refer to her general flamboyance and disregard for the set social expectations. This is backed up by the general opinion of her neighbors, with passages such as: "Neighbours of twenty or thirty years' standing said she had gone queer and wished herself too much." This is seen especially in the context of Hetty just living her best life, carrying around a baby carriage full of clothes she's selling, and having a fascination with train stations. The general public deemed her hobbies and lifestyle more or less unacceptable, particularly in defining the concept of respectability. This dismissal of Hetty as part of society and her alienation can be tied to principles of commodity fetishism, as she can't consume as much or commodify her labor in a way that would align with the capitalistic norms of the society she's part of. The job she chose can be interpreted as Hetty's attempt to fit into the system somehow, but how she goes about her work isn't seen as productive or good because the value of the clothing is not as desired. The value directly dictates her place in the world. The baby carriage doesn't count as a store, which, if it did, would help Hetty fit in a bit easier, and if the clothes were new and stylish, she would climb up the social hierarchy. This

means that Hetty's value as a person is directly tied to or at least masked by what she can offer as a commodity, which, in her case, is not much or desirable for the social context she lives in. This aspect digs Hetty into an even deeper hole of marginalization because society only views her through the lens of what she can sell, not her efforts and general condition.

"For they were all respectable people, with homes, good jobs, and cars. And Hetty was not respectable. These people said she had always been a bit strange when mentioning her." This quote is a testament that the abjection of Hetty is multifaceted and closely tied to what she can offer to society. As she lives in a council flat, which is government-provided housing, this already crashes her social points according to her children and broader society because older people who can't financially support themselves are a burden even their children don't want to deal with. Readers can also quickly pick up on the capitalist government's treatment of the poor population, especially the demographic that is on a pension because of age, which further digs Hetty into inescapable marginalization. "The blocks of flats were pioneers in that area, standing up grim, grey, hideous, among many acres of little houses and gardens, all soon to be demolished so that more tall grey blocks could replace them." The quote highlights the conditions of the council flats, especially how ignored and unkempt they are, again, because the people who live there cannot offer society something "of value" due to their expected demise. Poverty and the alienation of the people in it especially can be tied to commodity fetishism. The emphasis on ownership of certain goods defining your social standing directly impacts the population that cannot afford much, which leads to their stigmatization and, therefore, is part of Hetty's societal mistreatment.

These passages on the first page of the story are enough to indicate all the issues society has with Hetty; she's a gypsy, she's poor, old, and otherwise weird. She is quick to shut down any

negativity coming her way by embracing her identity more and more as the story progresses. However, just because she seems to reject all conventions and be proud in public, we see how much she struggles with herself through her treatment of her cat, Tibby.

Tibby is essential to the story, as he acts as the other "Other" and the only living being with whom she can converse freely. Tibby is a lot like Hetty; he is not much of a commodity, he's very rusty, and he's only had a home once Hetty came along and took him in. Their bond is also characterized by Hetty's projection of herself and her issues onto him, as evidenced by phrases such as: "I've been a good mother to you," she shouted to them before invisible witnesses-former neighbours, welfare workers, a doctor. "I never let you want for anything, never! When you were little you always had the best of everything! You can ask anybody; go on, ask them, then!." Clearly, she isn't directly talking to Tibby here but is addressing her children who abandoned her, but the projection doesn't end here. We can also observe her view of herself and her alienation through the conversation with her cat.

"Oh you are a clever puss, Tibby, Tibby! Oh you're clever, you are. You know how things are, don't you, you know how to get around and about." For example, this part of the conversation can be interpreted as Hetty praising herself, as she is also very quick on her feet and crafty with her clothing and her "career in sales," as she has to have a way to survive in harsh conditions. However, this praise of Tibby and herself is infrequent, with conversations such as ""You're filthy," she would say to him, setting the stew down to cool in his dish. "Filthy old thing. Eating that dirty old pigeon. What do you think you are, a wild cat? Decent cats don't eat dirty birds. Only those old gypsies eat wild birds,"" being the majority of their interactions.

The aforementioned part is also very much self-addressed. A cat, while it can definitely be dirty, cannot technically be a gypsy. Through these interactions, the readers get a deeper

glimpse at what is happening in Hetty's mind, which, in this case, is a clear sign of internalized abjection. From the general conversations and their themes, it will also be logical to conclude how Hetty sees her own marginalization and the reasons behind it: her ethnicity, age, and poverty. Her ethnicity especially seems to be a struggle for her, but it's important to mention that her stereotypical ideas about Romani people isn't even her own. The scrutiny faced by Romani people or "gypsies" is nothing new. "Ugly stereotypes formed already in the late medieval/early modern period. "Gypsies" were considered dirty, deceitful, too lazy to work, and prone to steal." These ideas were mainly linked to the more or less nomadic lifestyle of the Romani population and the fear that they were taking over local jobs by being excellent basket weavers (Dawsey, 2020). So it isn't hard to imagine how a person who is Romani and growing up in a society that shames their ethnicity would have false and negative beliefs about themselves deep down, internalizing them to a great degree. Even down to what she describes Tibby eating, which is a "dirty, old pigeon," ties not only to society's view of her ethnicity but the judgment of people who can't afford better food, again highlighting how abjection and commodity fetishism impact her story. Tibby is criticized not only for his status but specifically for being like Hetty by Hetty herself.

This entire story stresses the idea that abjection is intersectional and passed down from one generation to the other, whether that be her children or her cat. Hetty's character is defined by society only through what she can offer and what she is, neither of which are deemed "respectable enough." Through the lens of abjection, her marginalization becomes clear to the readers. Through commodity fetishism, we can understand how her financial state and work efficiency make the alienation that much worse. While examining her angsty monologues with Tibby, we unquestionably observe how the intersectionality of her abjection deeply troubled and

affected her and the course of her life. Her projection of her state onto Tibby is a reflection of decades of internalized shame for not only her Romani heritage, but also her financial status and career choices. By attempting to be herself as much as possible, Hetty became trapped in an endless cycle of alienation from which she was never given a chance to escape.

References

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